

Chestnut shell nano-adsorbent : Potential bioadsorbent for the removal of heavy metals from industrial wastewater

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Abstract : In this study chestnut shell was used as a potential adsorbent for the removal of heavy metals viz. lead (Pb) and zinc (Zn) from waste water. The characterization of the prepared adsorbent was done by IR spectral, SEM and BET analysis. The rate of adsorption was studied under different conditions, including pH (2–8), adsorbate dose (0.5–2 g), contact time (15–60 min) and the initial concentration of metal ions (25–100 mg/L). Maximum removal of Pb and Zn was attained at 1.5 g with 98.7% and 91% at 0.5 g at 60 min respectively. The adsorption data were well studied for adsorption isotherms and kinetic models and followed the second order kinetics and best fitted to Langmuir and Freundlich adsorption isotherm.

Keywords : Chestnut shell, lead, zinc, adsorption isotherms, wastewater.

Introduction

Water is a source of energy and life, although millions of people worldwide are suffering from the shortage of clean drinking and fresh water¹. Water pollution adversely affects not only aquatic plants and animal but it also affects human being and ecosystem. Water pollution is caused due to several reasons.

Major cause of water pollution such as sewage and wastewater, dumping, oil pollution, acid rain, global warming, industrial effluents^{2,3}. The major pollutants are heavy metals in ground, marine, industrial, and even treated wastewaters⁴. Discharge of toxic industrial wastes and untreated sanitary, dumping of industrial effluent, and runoff from agricultural fields could be the main sources of fresh water pollution. It is well known that 70 to 80% of all illnesses in developing countries are related to water contamination, particularly susceptible children and women. Heavy metals such as lead, zinc, nickel, mercury, cadmium, copper, arsenic, cobalt, chromium, bismuth, ferrous etc. have been recognized as poisonous to environment and human health even present in traces and so forth can damage liver and nerves and block func-

tion. However, high zinc can cause eminent health problems, such as stomach cramps, vomiting, skin irritations, anaemia, and nausea^{5,6}. The permissible limit of zinc and lead in drinking water is 5 mg L⁻¹ and 0.1 mg L⁻¹. These different methods are available to remove and isolate these heavy metals from water and wastewater such as ion-exchange, chemical precipitation, membrane filtration, adsorption, and electrochemical treatment technologies⁷. Adsorption is a well-known equilibrium separation process. It is now recognized effective, efficient and economic method for water decontamination application and for separation analytical purposes. The adsorbent may be of mineral, organic or biological origin activated carbon⁹⁻¹⁴, zeolites, microbial biomass¹⁶⁻²¹, silica beads^{20,21}, low-cost adsorbent industrial by-products²⁵⁻²⁷, agriculture waste^{18,23,24}, biomass^{32,33}, domestic food waste³⁴⁻³⁶ and polymeric materials (organic polymeric resins, macroporous hyper cross linked polymers are significant). For this research, chestnut shell was used as nano-adsorbent to remove Zn and Pb present in electroplating wastewater. The objective of this study was to investigate the adsorption potential of chestnut shell for the removal of

Pb ions and Zn ions from wastewater. The effect of several parameters such as contact time, initial concentration, pH value of the solution, adsorbent dose, volume and temperature were studied. The adsorption mechanisms of Pb and Zn ions onto chestnut shell evaluated in terms of thermodynamic and kinetics. The adsorption isotherms were described by using Langmuir and Freundlich models.

Experimental

For the present investigation, Chestnut shell (*Botanical name : Trapanatans* also known as singhada, pani-phal) were collected from Gwalior, and washed with distilled water for four to five times to remove dust and many other extra useless adhering particles. They were dried at room temperature in clean and neat space. After few days, it was dried in dry hot oven for one hour at 70 °C and then dried husk were grinded and powdered size by electric grinder and sieved. The sieved leaves 350 to 850 micrometers were used for experiments.

Instrumentation :

pH metric measurements were made on decibel DB 1011 digital pH meter fitted with a glass electrode, which was previously standardized with buffers of known pH in acidic and alkaline medium. The reaction kinetics was studied with the help of Systronics spectrophotometer (166) over the wavelength range of 340 to 990 nm.

Reagent and solutions :

Chestnut shell solution was prepared in distilled water. All chemicals were of analytical grade and used without further purification. Britton-Robinson buffers in the pH range 2.5 to 9.0 were prepared by adding suitable amount of 0.4 M NaOH solution to the stock solution of 2.14 mL of phosphoric acid, 2.3 mL acetic acid and 2.472 g of boric acid. Solutions were stirred after mixing and left overnight to attain equilibrium.

Procedure :

Adsorption studies were performed by the batch technique at 25, 50, 75 and 100 ppm concentration. Adsorption isotherms recorded at a fixed pH range (2.5–12.0) over the temperature range 30–35 °C. Adsorption was achieved by adding a known amount of each adsorbent into the metal solution of known concentration and pH,

and the conical flask were agitated intermittently. The data obtained in the batch mode studies were used to calculate the equilibrium metal adsorption amount. Once the equilibrium was established, supernatant liquid was filtered off using Whatmann filter paper No. 41 and uptake of the metal was determined spectrophotometrically by measuring the absorbance at 429 nm.

Results and discussion

Adsorbent characterization :

The physiochemical characteristics of the nano-adsorbents were important in order to evaluate their adsorption capacities. The brief outlines of the characterization techniques employed in the present investigation were given below.

Infrared spectra :

The infrared spectral assignment of chestnut shell nano-adsorbent (*Trapanatans*) was obtained by KBr disc method using FT infrared spectroscopy, 4100 JASCO, Japan. The absorption bands identified in the spectra and their assignment to the corresponding functional groups are shown in the Table 1.

Table 1. IR bands of nano-adsorbent *Trapanatans*

Position	Assignment (cm ⁻¹)
3420b	O-H stretch
2922s	C-H stretch
1742s	C=O stretch
1639m	N-H bend
1517s	N-O stretch
1266m	C-H wag

m = medium, s = strong, b = broad.

BET analysis :

The leaves of chestnut shell nano-adsorbent (*Trapanatans*) were analyzed by using NOVA Model. BET analysis technique was carried out using surface area.

Table 2. BET analysis of bio-adsorbent

Sl. No.	Particle size (µm)	Bulk density (kg/m ³)	Surface area (m ² /g)	Porosity
Chest nut shell (<i>Trapanatans</i>)	153	0.23	32.43	0.35

Surface topography (SEM) :

The surface morphology of the bio-adsorbent was examined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The surface of *Trapanatans* was studied by SEM JSM-6510LV. The samples for SEM was prepared by lightly sprinkling the powder on a double adhesive tape stuck to an aluminium stab. The stubs were then coated with gold to a thickness of about 300 Å under an argon atmosphere using a gold sputter module in a high-vacuum evaporator. The coated samples were then randomly scanned using a scanning electron microscope Jeol : JSM-6510LV and photomicrographs were taken (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. SEM image of chestnut shell (*Trapanatans*).

Removal of Pb and Zn using chestnut shell (*Trapanatans*) :

Effect of pH :

The pH plays an important role in the adsorption process by affecting the surface charge of adsorbent, the degree of ionization and species of the adsorbent. Thus the effect of pH in the solutions on the removal efficiency of lead was studied at different pH ranging from 2.0 to 8.0 under the precise condition. Results were shown in Fig. 2. The low removal efficiency at low pH was apparently due to the presence of higher concentration of H^+ in the solution which competes with the Pb ions for the adsorption sites of the chestnut shell. With the increase in pH, the H^+ concentration decreases leading to increased lead uptake.

At low pH values, the surface of the adsorbent would

be closely associated with hydroxonium ions (H_3O^+), by repulsive forces, to the surface functional groups, consequently decreasing the percentage removal of metal. As the solution pH increases, the onset of the metal hydrolysis and the precipitation began at $pH > 7$ and the onset of adsorption therefore occurs before the beginning of hydrolysis. When the pH of the adsorbing medium was increased from 2 to 8, there was a corresponding increase in de-protonation of the adsorbent surface, leading to a decrease in H^+ ion on the adsorbent surface. This creates more negative charges on the adsorbent surface, which favours adsorption of positively charge species and the positive sites on the adsorbent surface. It was observed from the experiment that the maximum uptake of Pb and Zn takes place at pH 2.8, almost >95% removal observed in case of chestnut shell. Similarly the adsorption of zinc was studied in the pH range 2–8 under the precise conditions (contact time of 15 min, rotation speed 150 rpm with 1 g of the adsorbents was used). It was observed that with increase in the pH (2–8) of the wastewater, the percentage removal of metal ions (lead and zinc) increased up to the pH 8. The results were shown in Fig. 2.

Effect of adsorbents dosage :

The availability and accessibility of adsorption site is controlled by adsorbent dosage. Adsorbent dosage was varied from 0.5 g to 2 g, under the specific conditions

Fig. 2. Effect of pH on % of biosorption of lead and zinc for chestnut shell (*Trapanatans*). Conditions (adsorbent dose = 1 g, contact time = 15 min, conc. of metal = 25 ppm, rotation speed = 150 rpm and temp. = 35 °C).

(pH = 8, conc. of metal = 25 ppm, rotation speed = 150 rpm and temperature of 35 °C). It was observed that the percentage removal of lead and zinc increases with the increase in the adsorbent dosage (Fig. 3). The percentage removal of lead and zinc by different dose of chestnut shell (*Trapanatans*) were 88, 91, 98.9, 97% respectively while maximum removal of Pb was attained at 1.5 g with 98.9% and the removal of Zn increases gradually from 91% at 0.5 g/100 mL up to 86% at 2.0 g/100 mL. These findings were depicted in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Effect of adsorbent dose on % of biosorption of lead and zinc for chestnut shell (*Trapanatans*). Conditions (pH = 8, conc. of metal = 25 ppm, rotation speed = 150 rpm and temp. = 35 °C).

Effect of contact time and initial metal ion concentration :

The relationship between contact time and the percentage removal of heavy metals from wastewater with chestnut shell (*Trapanatans*) were shown in Fig. 4. The effect of contact time was studied at a room temperature of 35 °C, at intervals of 15 min. From the obtained result, it is evident that the removal of metal ions increased as contact time increases. Pb was removed using the produced adsorbent. The results showed that the removal efficiency of lead decreased from 98.9% to 85.5% with increasing the initial lead concentration from 25 to 100 mg/L. The decrease in the percentage removal of lead can be explained with the fact that the bio sorbents had limited active sites, which would have become saturated above a certain concentration.

The result showed that (Fig. 4), the removal rate for

Fig. 4. Effect of (a) contact time and (b) initial metal ion conc. of % of biosorption of lead and zinc on chestnut shell nano adsorbent (*Trapanatans*). Conditions (pH = 8, adsorbent dose = 1 g, contact time = 15 min, rotation speed = 150 rpm and temp. = 35 °C).

Pb was rapid within the first 15 min sharply and gets increased for another 60 min. The initial faster rate may be due to the availability of the uncovered surface area of the adsorbents, since the adsorption kinetics depends on the surface area of the adsorbents. On the other hand, % of removal for lead increased gradually with increasing contact time. The lead adsorption takes place at the more reactive sites. As these sites were progressively filled, the more difficult the sorption becomes, and the sorption process tends to be more unfavourable. In case of Zn effect of initial concentration was studied by varying the heavy metal concentration, from 25 to 100 mg/L with 1.0 g of adsorbent, at contact time of 15 min at pH 8. The decrease in % removal biosorption may be caused by the lack of sufficient surface area of adsorbent to accommodate much more Zn ions available in the solution.

Table 3. The data of Langmuir and Freundlich sorption constants for biosorption of Pb and Zn ions on chestnut shell (*Trapanatans*)

Metal ions	Langmuir constants			Freundlich constants		
	Q_e^0 (mg g ⁻¹)	b (L mg ⁻¹)	R^2	K_F	N	R^2
Pb	2.31	0.526	0.972	0.9015	3.21	0.994
Zn	2.35	0.609	0.972	0.9749	3.43	0.991

Adsorption isotherms :

The adsorption isotherm for lead and zinc was studied using initial concentrations of metal at 100 ppm, pH = 8, temperature at 35 °C and amount of adsorbent dosage (0.5–2.0 g/100 ml). The data obtained were fitted to the Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms. These models were tested to determine the maximal capacity of lead and zinc removal using chestnut shell. The quality of the isotherm fit to the Langmuir equation, in the linear form was written as :

$$\frac{C_e}{Q_e} = \frac{1}{bq_{max}} + \frac{C_e}{q_{max}} \tag{1}$$

where C_e was the equilibrium concentration of metal ions (mg/L), Q_e was the amount of metal ions adsorbed per unit weight of adsorbent (mg/g bentonite), q_{max} was the maximum adsorption capacity (mg/g), and b was the adsorption equilibrium constant (L/mg).

For the Freundlich equation, the linear form was written as :

$$\log q_e = \log K + \frac{1}{n} \log C_e \tag{2}$$

where K and n were the constant characteristics of the system.

The best estimated values of all the equation parameters were summarized in Table 3. The adsorption isotherm data were well fitted with both the linearized Langmuir and Freundlich equations and the data were obtained from that equation for lead and zinc were as shown in Figs. 5(a), (b) and 6(a), (b). The value of R^2 was higher for Freundlich isotherm than the Langmuir isotherm; that means Freundlich equation represented the adsorption process very well. Values of K_F , $1/n$, Q_0 and b were given in Table 3.

Rate kinetics :

The kinetic parameters for the adsorption process were studied on the batch adsorption at room temperature, initial lead and zinc concentration of 100 ppm, biomass dosage was 1.0 g and the initial solution pH was kept at 8.0. The adsorption data was fitted into first order and second order kinetics. The first order equation was plotted for $\ln(q_e - q_t)$ against t . The values of $\ln(q_e - q_t)$ were calculated from the kinetic data. This is shown in Fig. 7(a) and (b). The k_1 values were calculated from the slope of this plot. The value of k_1 was shown in Table 4. The second

Fig. 5. (a) Langmuir isotherms plot for adsorption of zinc onto adsorbent chestnut shell (*Trapanatans*) and (b) Freundlich isotherms plot for adsorption of zinc onto adsorbent chestnut shell (*Trapanatans*).

Fig. 6. (a) Langmuir isotherms plot for adsorption of lead onto adsorbent chestnut shell and (b) Freundlich isotherms plot for adsorption of lead onto adsorbent chestnut shell (*Trapanatans*).

Fig. 7. (a) First order plots adsorption kinetics of Pb and Zn on adsorbent chestnut shell (*Trapanatans*) and (b) second order plots adsorption kinetics of Pb and Zn on adsorbent chestnut shell (*Trapanatans*).

Table 4. Comparison of pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order kinetic parameters for biosorption of Pb and Zn ions by chestnut shell (*Trapanatans*) at different experimental conditions

Metal ions	Conc. (mg/L)	Pseudo-first order			Pseudo-second order			
		q_e (Calcd.) (mg g ⁻¹)	K_1 (min ⁻¹)	R^2	q_e (Calcd.) (mg g ⁻¹)	K_2 (g mg ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)	h (mg g ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)	R^2
Pb	100 ppm	1.358	0.034	0.980	2.1691	0.0868	0.4088	0.963
	75 ppm	1.037	0.036	0.977	1.7094	0.1225	0.3580	0.970
	50 ppm	0.6714	0.034	0.984	1.1947	0.1872	0.2722	0.974
	25 ppm	0.3630	0.036	0.958	0.6230	0.3670	0.1426	0.974
Zn	100 ppm	1.819	0.039	0.933	2.2371	0.0635	0.3182	0.938
	75 ppm	1	0.034	0.986	1.7301	0.1213	0.3631	0.970
	50 ppm	0.6918	0.036	0.969	1.2048	0.1794	0.2604	0.973
	25 ppm	0.3265	0.032	0.978	0.6242	0.3763	0.1466	0.974

order equation was plotted for t/q_t against t . The values of q_e and k_2 were calculated from the slope and intercept of this plot. The values of q_e and k_2 were shown in Table 4. A good agreement of the experimental data with the second order kinetic model was observed.

The correlation coefficient for the second order kinetic model is 0.999 and the calculated q_e values agree very well with the experimental data. Thus, a plot of t/q_t against t should give a linear relationship with a slope of $1/q_e$.

Conclusion

The non-carbon, nano-adsorbent (NA) were successfully used for the adsorption and removal of heavy metals from waste water. The present study offers major advantage of the NA were used without any previous activation treatment which decreases adsorption costs. The adsorption characteristics of heavy metals onto NA were evaluated in terms of equilibrium, kinetic, thermodynamic parameters and second-order equation. All parameters have been successfully applied to predict dynamical behaviour for the adsorption of the heavy metals on the NA. The desired removal of metal can be achieved by choosing the predicted conditions using the developed models.

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